

The Level of Ability for Career Decision Making Among A Sample of High School Students and its Effect on Their Future Profession

Anas Mohammad Nawafleh, Hussein M. A. AL- Tarawneh, Haya Hussien M. Tarawneh

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 09, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Career Decision Making, High School Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5086550</p>	<p><i>This research aimed to identify the level of ability to choose a career among a sample of high school students and its effect on their future profession. The sample included (131).High school male and female students selected using the stratified random method and the career decision-making skill scale were applied. Results indicated that the level of career choice-making skill among high school students was medium for the skill's whole dimensions except for the traditional dimension that came at a high level. The findings also indicated statistically significant differences between the means of the career choice-making skill dimensions for high school students based on the variable of gender for the total score of the dimensions as a whole except for the traditional dimension. In addition, the results indicated statistically significant differences between the means of the career choice-making skill dimensions for high school students based on the variable of the academic stage.</i></p>

Introduction

The decision-making process regarding students' selection for the appropriate professional is one of the most important decisions for them and for organizations and individuals' lives. Its importance impacts human life, including work and stability, and the various areas of human activities (Alsawwat, 2010). Therefore, the decision-making process requires a lot of preparations and arrangements, which can be done through organized guidance, leading to increased positive aspirations among students. Moreover, it affects students' tendencies and patterns of behavior and develops various mental, emotional, and social aspects of their personalities. Vocational counseling is a process related to both human and professional dimensions concerned with educated individuals and the work through which they aspire to achieve their potential and realize the effect of their decision on their future profession (Abu Hammad, 2008). Career choice is not an easy decision for individuals to make since it is related to their future. Parents have a great role in guiding their children to choose their future profession, as the parents' educational and cultural backgrounds assist in understanding their children's desires regardless of their gender differences. This happens through deep conversations with the children about the importance of work in any individual's life, explaining labor market opportunities available, and providing them with accurate professional information to be conscious, self-fulfilling, and consistent with their choice for future profession requirements. The rational professional decision taken in a logical manner in which the individual's interests, abilities, and aspirations are taken into account leads to their happiness, contentment, and professional ambition, which contributes to their success and development (Jawdat&Al-ezza,2012). The difficulty of taking any decision is based on the learners' ability to use their performance skills, intellectual capabilities, and personal characteristics to develop distinct strategies, create multiple innovative solutions, and select the choice which is most in line with their goals, desires, requirements, society, values, and norms. This helps individuals maintain their compatibility with themselves and the society they belong to (Eysenck&Keane,2000).

On the other hand, the individual's inability to make a decision related to choosing a career may be due to a difficulty that may arise before or after the decision-making process, such as the lack of preparation measures taken by teenagers and the lack of information or its inaccuracy on the decision-making process, its stages, capabilities and essential considerations related to the profession and its specialties. This may be due to several factors, including the development of intelligence and capabilities such as the qualitative development in mental processes, the ability to rebound thinking, the ability to generalize and think about different alternatives simultaneously, and the capability for future planning. Teenagers can make decisions based on rationality and methodology, and they tend to think realistically. However, because of the lack of life experience and maturity and the lack of individual skills, their decisions are often unbalanced, which sometimes impedes them from taking the appropriate decision or make incorrect decisions (Gati&Krausz, 1996).

Research problem:

From the researcher's view, students in secondary schools are different from others at different levels/grades regarding their need for vocational counseling. This may be due to their approach to professional decision-making and determining their views of the future profession. Additionally, deciding on the individual's future profession is challenging, especially for this segment of people, due to the lack of information, or due to following traditional methods, or due to being dependent on others. Therefore, these factors may affect the individual's professional decision-making process when selecting the specialization. They wish to study to be able to get the required career. Here, some problems may occur, and students should identify them before making a career decision. Given the facts mentioned above, this study aims to identify the problems students face in the process of career decision-making and offer solutions for these problems.

Implications of the Study

The theoretical importance of this research lies in the fact that it focuses on high school students, as it is a critical stage for this segment to select their future profession. Moreover, this research helps to enrich the theoretical literature along with the rapid technological development. The scientific importance of this research lies in its value to provide feedback for students on how they can learn and be prepared for deciding related to their future profession. In addition, the decision-makers can benefit from it and officials in the psychological counseling field who can contribute in preparing counseling programs aiming to identify obstacles and challenges faced by students in making decisions related to their future professions.

Research Objectives

This research aims to achieve the following objectives:

- First, identifying the extent to which high school students possess career decision-making skills based on the career choice-making scale.
- Identifying students' differences based on their gender, academic stage, and father's profession

Research questions:

- To what extent do high school students possess career decision-making skills?
- Are there any statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students' levels on the career decision-making scale that are attributed to the variable of gender?
- Are there any statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students' level on the career decision-making scale attributed to the academic stage's variable?

Limitations the study

- The current study is stated by subjective borders- High school students in the UAE.
- Location: UAE, Mohammed Bin Zayed City.
- Timing: - Second term (2019-2020).
- Research tools borders: The measurement of taking vocational decision.

Procedural Definitions of Terms:

Career decision-making: A process that responds to the emergence of a problem or discrepancy between the current and the desired phase, which requires considering an alternative pathway (Stephen & Timohy, 2006, p: 166). Procedurally, in this study, it is the participant's score on the career decision-making scale utilized here.

- High school students: students at grades from ninth to twelfth who prepare to start their professional life and assume their roles in society. This study is procedurally defined as all 10th and 11th students at Elite Private School in Abu Dhabi, UAE.

Theoretical literature and previous studies

The process of decision-making is the basis upon which most contemporary life matters are built (AlBlooshi, 2007), and it is considered difficult due to many factors, including family conditions, customs, traditions as well as the psychological, economic, and social motives and aspects (Al-Issawi, 1986). Moreover, the ability to make career decisions develops the individual's sense of excitement and suspense. Neglecting this aspect results in many mistakes that may negatively affect the future of many students (Habib, 1997). The most important considerations that affect the professional decision as mentioned by (Alkhatatneh 2011). are:

1. The individual himself/herself: The individual's total previous experiences, his/her psychological and social status, values, beliefs, and future aspirations play a significant role in influencing decision-making, either positively or negatively.
2. The immediate and surrounding circumstances: among which the individual's life including members, groups, systems, customs, and traditions in which they belong to.
3. The indirect experiences and circumstances: everything that indirectly affects the decision-making process, such as internal and external information and guidance
4. The decision-making system: As explained by (Barbar, 1996, pp. 165-168). the basic steps for

professional decision-making are as follows:

- First of all, recognizing and defining the problem;
- Second, identifying the alternatives, which requires innovative alternatives/solutions to solve the problem;
- Third, evaluating the alternatives, which means that the strengths and weaknesses of each alternative should be determined and assessed;
- Fourth, select the ideal alternative among the possible available alternatives;
- Finally, the implementation of the decision, which is considered the beginning of the solution.

There have been many studies conducted on the current research topic, among which, the study of (Al-Khazali, 2019), aimed to identify the psychological pressure amongst middle school students. This study was tested on (400). male and female students, and the results indicated that there were differences between members of the sample regarding deciding according to the gender variable, and these differences were in favor of male students. (Sawaleh,2019). investigated the level of professionalism in making decisions and its patterns among university students. The study sample consisted of 100 university students, and the results indicated no differences in the level of professionalism in making decisions between students of social sciences and law. (Al-Zabin & Abu-Asaad's ,2017). the study aimed to identify career choice decision-making among high school students. The sample consisted of (474).Male and female students and the results indicated that high school students scored higher on making decisions related to their future careers regarding both the total score and the dimensions' score, which included the desire. It was also indicated that the career choice decision-making process differs based on gender in favor of females in the desire and total score of dimensions. (Al-Zahra,2016). the study indicated that the level of ability to make a decision related to career choice for fourth-year college students according to their gender and father's job variables was medium for outstanding students among a sample of 160 male and female students, and also no apparent differences were indicated in the ability to make a decision-based gender.

In the study of (Shumba & Naong,2012).Which aimed at identifying factors affecting students' career choice through individual aspirations on a sample of (133).students, it was revealed that self-education and teachers played an important role in students' career choices. (Al-Saadi,2012). conducted a study to identify students' maturity in making decisions related to their career choice and its relation to the professional decision-making. The study sample consisted of 286 male and female high school students (grades, 11& 12). The results indicated no statistically significant differences between the average degree-professional maturity between male and female students in the two grades students.

(Muhammad et al., 2010) surveyed the impact of contextual aspects on student planning and career development. The study sample consisted of (1436).Male and female students from (22). technical schools. The study results showed that the contextual factors influenced the students' professional decision-making process. Also, the absence of role models in the family and the lack of professional information affected the students' career choices.(Nota & Soresi,2004).conducted a study to verify the effectiveness of a counseling program in improving problem-solving skills and career choice decision making. The study sample included 156 male and female students, and results revealed that providing this type of program, which was designed to increase efficiency,would positively affect the decision-making process. It would also help reduce the level of hesitation among teenagers when deciding to choose their careers. (Favini,2004).

Investigated the impact of counseling programs to explore the relationship between the educational system and career choice. The study sample consisted of 87 male and female students and resulted in the fact that most of the students were satisfied with their guidance by psychological counselors. (Finally, et al., 2011). conducted a study to identify the relationship between career decision-making and self-efficacy among a sample of (234).Male and female university students, the results showed that the students whose grades were low on the self-efficacy measure were more hesitant to decide about their career choice.

Methodology

Study population and sample

The study population included all high school male and female students in UAE's schools, from which a sample of the study consists of (131). male and female students (81) male and (50) female students. Of Elite Private School, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates Grades (11) and (12) who followed the UAE's Ministry of Education curriculum for the year 2019/2020 and included (table 1).

Table 1: The sample's demographics

Variable	Category	Count	Percentage
Gender	Males	81	61.83%
	Females	50	38.17%
	Total	131	100%
Grade	11th	58	44.27%

	12th	73	55.73%
	Total	131	100%

Instrument of the Study

After reviewing the theoretical literature and the related early studies on the topic, such as the Alnawfleh study (2014), the researcher developed the scale of career choice decision-making skill and the questionnaire consisting of (34) items in its final version and was electronically distributed to participants.

Instrument Reliability

Correlation coefficients of the instrument were calculated using the Cronbach alpha, and table (2) below shows the result for the career choice decision-making skill scale reliability among high school male and female students.

Table 2: Reliability analysis on the study variables using Cronbach Alpha

Dimensions	No.of items	Cronbach Alpha
Availability of information	5	0.877
Traditional Dimension: Deciding on the future profession	11	0.859
Independency in making a career choice decision	8	0.872
Involvement of others in making a career choice decision	10	0.910
Total	34	0.933

Table (2) shows that the lowest value was for the Traditional Dimension in deciding regarding the future profession, which was (0.859), and all the other values reflected high levels of reliability given that the highest value was (0.910) for the dimension of involvement of others in making a career choice decision. These values reflect the appropriateness of the instrument for our study.

Results and Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the extent of career choice decision-making skills among high school students on a sample of 131 high school male and female students; the study used a 34-items questionnaire as a tool of the study " Career Choice Decision-Making Skill Among High School Students " and included four dimensions (skills): Availability of information (5 items), Traditional Dimension (11 items), deciding on the future profession, Independency in making a career choice decision (8 items), and involvement of others in making a career choice decision (10 items).

Results related to the 1st research question: To what extent do high school students possess career decision-making skills?

To answer this question, means and standard deviations for each skill of the career choice decision making skill were used as well, as a triple rating scale was used to describe the means values' levels (low, medium, high) as follows:

* 1.00 – 2.33 (low). * 2.34-3.64 (medium) * 3/65-5.00 (high)

These classification categories were obtained based on the following formula:

$$\text{Category Length} = \frac{\text{Response Highest Weight} - \text{Response Lowest Weight}}{\text{Number of Rating Categories}}$$

$$\text{Category Length} = \frac{5 - 1}{3} = 1.33$$

Table 3: Means, Standard deviations, and MI for 'career choice decision making skill' (listed in descending order)

No.	Aspects	m	SD	MI	Level	Rank
1	Traditional Dimension: Deciding regarding the future profession	3.81	0.60	76.20	High	1
2	Availability of information	3.56	0.86	71.20	moderate	2
3	Independency in making a career choice decision	3.52	0.75	70.40	moderate	3
4	Involvement of others in making a career choice decision	3.46	0.79	69.20	moderate	4
	Making the career choice decision	3.59	0.59	71.80	moderate	

Mean description (1.00 – 2.33 low, 2.34 – 3.67 moderate, 3.67 – 5.00 high)

Table (3) indicates the values of Mean, Standard Deviation, and MI for making the career choice decision dimensions, with the 'availability of Information' dimension having the highest mean value compared to the other dimensions reaching a value of (3.81). On the other hand, the 'Involving others in making a professional decision' dimension had the least mean value (3.46). The overall score for the 'career choice decision making scale' was (3.59), expressing a medium level of agreement among respondents.

The researcher believes that eleventh and twelfth-grade students do not always make rational decisions and do not consider them. This result may be attributed to the lack of awareness of the importance of the decision or their dependence on other people they trust, such as parents, siblings, and friends, keeping in mind that some of these students may not desire to pursue a professional career in the future.

The availability of information is considered the main pillar for students to make a career choice decision. If the information is little or not available, students will not choose or make a wise decision on their future profession. But, on the other hand, if the information is available, the student will be able to make a better decision regarding choosing their future career according to their capabilities, desires, and aspirations.

Analyzing the career choice decision making skill for high school students based on the four dimensions of the skill:

1st: The Availability of Information Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making:

Means and standard deviations for the availability of information dimension in Career Choice Decision Making were calculated as shown in table (4) below:

Table 4: Means and standard deviations for the items of the availability of information dimension (in descending order)

No.	Items	Mean	SD	MI	level	Rank
5	I review all the professions available in the market before choosing one of them.	3.71	1.01	74.20	high	1
4	I need to learn and acquire all the details related to a profession before practicing it.	3.66	1.03	73.20	moderate	2
3	I feel that the information available on the careers' specific requirements is insufficient.	3.52	1.12	70.40	moderate	3
1	I study the professions' related options, which I have before making a career choice decision.	3.51	1.04	70.20	moderate	4
2	I seek to obtain enough information on professions matching my capabilities before I make a career choice decision.	3.38	1.05	67.60	moderate	5
	Availability of information in making a career choice decision	3.56	0.86	71.20	moderate	

Means description (1.00 – 2.33 low, 2.34 – 3.67 moderate, 3.67 – 5.00 high)

Table (4) indicates that the level of the availability of information. Availability in career choice decision making was medium with a mean of (3.56) and relative importance of (71.20), and the levels of the dimension's items ranged between medium and high (3.38 - 3.71). Item no. 5, which states "I review all the professions available in the market before choosing one of them," came first with the highest mean of (3.71) with a relative importance of (3.71) while item no. 2 states, "I seek to obtain enough information on professions matching my capabilities before I make a career choice decision" came last with a mean of (3.38) with a relative importance of (67.60) according to respondents.

The availability of information is a basic base for clarifying the image for the student, and the less information is given, the less ability the student has to decide or choose. Thus, whenever enough information is available, the

student will have a clear image and hence can decide their career based on their capabilities, desires, and future aspirations, so detailed information is necessary to help make accurate decisions related to a future career.

2nd: The Traditional Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making:

Means and standard deviations for the traditional dimension in Career Choice Decision Making were calculated as shown in table (5) below:

Table 5: Means and standard deviations for the items of the availability of information dimension (in descending order):

No.	Items	Mean	SD	MI	level	Rank
15	I look forward to advancing my career in the future.	4.04	0.78	80.80	high	1
7	I must try a couple of different professions before choosing one.	3.98	0.81	79.60	high	2
13	I tend to choose an easy profession, which suits my physical and intellectual capabilities.	3.96	0.90	79.20	high	3
6	I am convinced with my peers' opinion regarding the choice of my future profession.	3.92	0.91	78.40	high	4
14	I prefer to work within the region I live in.	3.92	0.77	78.40	high	4
16	My profession is decided upon the customs and traditions in the place where I live.	3.90	0.91	78.00	high	6
12	Choosing my profession depends on its position among other professions.	3.82	1.00	76.40	high	7
8	I believe that the qualities I have acquired from my parents will help and motivate me to choose my profession.	3.74	0.92	74.80	high	8
10	I worry when I am asked to decide on my career path.	3.63	0.99	72.60	moderate	9
9	I wish that the Counselor selects the future profession for me.	3.60	1.05	72.00	moderate	10
11	I seek to choose a profession with high income, regardless of the difficulties associated with it.	3.40	1.19	68.00	moderate	11
	The traditional way in taking the professional decision	3.81	0.60	76.20	high	

Means description (1.00 – 2.33 low, 2.34 – 3.67 moderate, 3.67 – 5.00 high)

Table (5) indicates that the level of the traditional dimension in deciding on a future career was high, and a total mean of (3.81) and relative importance of (76.20) and means ranged between (3.40) and (4.04). Item no. 15, which states "I look forward to advancing my career in the future," came first with a mean of (4.04) while item no. 11 which states, "I seek to choose a profession with high income, regardless of the difficulties associated with it" came last with a mean of (3.40) according to respondents. Thus, the overall score representing the traditional method in making career-related decisions is rated by a mean of (3.81), expressing a high level of agreement amongst the study sample.

The researcher believes that making a career choice decision based on the traditional method is considered incompetent and will not benefit the student because it is based on old-style references, such as choosing a career based on others' experiences and then if it does not work, then they can change the profession. This method also relies very much on the customs and traditions, which may not match the current market. In determining the future plight and profession, the future is traditionally determined according to the student's physical ability. For example, or based on its proximity to its environment, place of residence, and other facts that are not related to other concepts such as the development of this profession and the psychological and material return of the profession as well as the social status and other things that are away from the traditional aspects mentioned above.

3rd: The Independency Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making:

Means and standard deviations for the Independency Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making were calculated as shown in table (6) below:

Table 6: Means and standard deviations for the items of the Independency Dimension (in descending order)

No.	Items	M	SD	MI	level	Rank
19	I make my own decision, and I feel it is appropriate when it comes to choosing my profession.	3.68	0.95	73.60	high	1

23	I can make decisions in any profession at any time.	3.61	1.03	72.20	moderate	2
22	I set an example for myself in choosing my future profession.	3.60	1.01	72.00	moderate	3
20	I choose the profession that I am convinced with, regardless of its income.	3.50	1.03	70.00	moderate	4
24	I am interested in making appropriate professional decisions.	3.50	1.06	70.00	moderate	4
17	I am responsible for the decision I make regarding my profession.	3.45	1.12	69.00	moderate	6
18	I feel depressed when I fail to make the right decision.	3.45	1.08	69.00	moderate	6
21	I care about the promotions' scale in the profession that I am choosing.	3.33	0.98	66.60	moderate	8
	Independency in making a career choice decision	3.52	0.75	70.40	moderate	

Means description (1.00 – 2.33 low, 2.34 – 3.67 moderate, 3.67 – 5.00 high)

Table (6) indicates the means, standard deviation, and MI's values for the Independency dimension in making a career choice decision, and it indicates that the total level for this dimension came medium with a mean of (3.52) and relative importance of (70.40). The means of this dimension were distributed between medium and high levels with means ranging from (3.33) and (3.68) with item no. 19, which states 'I make my own decision, which I feel is appropriate when it comes to choosing my profession' first reaching a mean of (3.68) and relative importance of (73.60). While item no. 21 states 'I care about the promotions' scale in the profession, I am choosing' last with a mean of (3.33) and relative importance of (66.60) based on participants' responses.

Independency in making a career choice decision is a goal that educators and parents focus on to help students make a proper career choice decision. Therefore, if the student can make the student independent in his/her decision, the student's ability to take responsibility for professional decision-making and independence may be arranged in professional decision-making with certain references that are role models for this student. For example, the independence may be stemming from the student's reliance on a specific area that he sees in the future profession. In all cases, the student must be assisted in ensuring independence to avoid a negative impact on the student, leading him/her to hesitation, fear, or depression.

4th: The Involvement Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making:

Means and standard deviations for the Involvement Dimension in Career Choice Decision Making were calculated as shown in table (7) below:

Table 7: Means and standard deviations for the items of the Involvement Dimension (in descending order)

No.	Items	m	sd	MI	level	Rank
25	I carefully plan for my future career	3.69	0.95	73.80	high	1
28	I see that I am only suitable for one career.	3.58	1.02	71.60	moderate	2
26	I think that choosing a career is imperative.	3.56	1.02	71.20	moderate	3
31	It seems that the continuous changes in my life conditions make me unstable regarding one career.	3.53	0.98	70.60	moderate	4
32	I think I am not concerned about selecting a career because my parents select it for me.	3.48	1.12	69.60	moderate	5
27	I think I am a hesitant person when it comes to career choice decision-making.	3.44	1.11	68.80	moderate	6
29	I feel that I can't choose a specific career by myself.	3.44	1.08	68.80	moderate	7
34	I choose my friends' careers when I choose one for me.	3.44	1.14	68.80	moderate	8
33	I consult professionals to ask about the professions that fall within my choices.	3.30	1.06	66.00	moderate	9
30	I think I can't stay in one career position for a long time	3.14	1.11	62.80	moderate	10
	Involvement of others in making a career choice decision:	3.46	0.79	69.20	moderate	

Means description (1.00 – 2.33 low, 2.34 – 3.67 moderate, 3.67 – 5.00 high)

Table (7) indicates that the level of involvement of others in making a career choice decision was medium as the total mean was (3.46) with a relative importance of (69.20). The means the dimension's item ranged between medium and high (3.14 – 3.69). Item no. 25, which states " I carefully plan for the future career," came first with a mean of (3.69) and relative importance of (73.80), while item no. 30 states, " I think I can't stay in one career position for a long time " came last with a mean of (3.14) and relative importance of (62.80).

The researcher believes that engaging the students in decision-making is necessary to consolidate the previous information about the future profession and promote the trend towards a profession to be chosen later. Also, the student's participation in choosing the future profession helps the student not hesitate to take his decision. The researcher adds that referring to the specialists to ask about the profession's professions is necessary and is considered an important element in the student's participation in deciding for the future profession. Furthermore, the researcher believes that the parents' participation is regarded as an essential and effective element in the student's participation to decide on the future career so that it helps him/her take a more precise picture before the decision.

Results related to the 2nd research question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students' level on career decision-making scale attributed to the variable of gender?

To answer this question, means, standard deviations, and t values as shown in table (8) below:

Table 8:t-test results' means and SDs for taking the career decision based on gender

Aspects	gender	No	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Availability of Information	Males	81	3.75	0.74	3.45	0.001
	Females	50	3.24	0.95		
The traditional way to take the professional decision	Males	81	3.88	0.61	1.63	0.104
	Females	50	3.70	0.58		
Independency in making a career choice decision	Males	81	3.65	0.66	2.64	0.009
	Females	50	3.30	0.84		
Involvement of others in making a career choice decision	Males	81	3.58	0.74	2.31	0.022
	Females	50	3.26	0.84		
Taking the professional decision	Males	81	3.72	0.52	3.31	0.001
	Females	50	3.38	0.64		

Table (8) indicates statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) value between the means of the career choice decision making skill dimensions among high school students based on the variable of gender according to calculated t-value, which reached (3.31) at a significance of (0.001) for the total score, for the dimension of availability of information, the t value was (3.45) at a significance of (0.001). For the independence dimension, the value was (2.64) with a significance of (0.009), and a value of (2.31), and a significance of (0.022) for the involvement dimension, and these differences were in favor of male students. For the traditional dimension, there were no statistically significant differences at the value ($\alpha = 0.05$) between male and female students as the mean was (1.63) with a significance of (0.104).

The researcher believes that the superiority of males over females in the fields of professional decision-making for the future profession stems from the nature of the Arab community that holds male responsibility in life, as males are primarily responsible in all areas of life. Therefore, the role of females comes second, and the difference between males and females has been observed in all the dimensions of decision-making, except the traditional field of decision-making, where the researcher believes that females and males alike have not reached full independence, especially males in their professional decision-making, as the parents intervene. The age is close, and there is no clear perception by most of them. This has to do with a future life, and therefore, opinions converged between male and female participants on the traditional dimension of the professional decision-making among participants.

Results related to the 3rd research question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students' level on career decision-making scale attributed to the variable of the academic stage?

To answer this question, means, standard deviations, and t values as shown in table (9) below:

Table 9:t-test results, means, and SDs for taking the career decision based on an academic level

Dimensions	Academic level	No	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Availability of Information	11 th	58	3.25	0.86	3.85	0.000
	12 th	73	3.80	0.78		
The traditional way to take the professional decision	11 th	58	3.63	0.53	3.21	0.002
	12 th	73	3.96	0.62		
Independency in making a career choice decision	11 th	58	3.34	0.79	2.43	0.016
	12 th	73	3.66	0.69		
Involvement of others in making a career choice decision	11 th	58	3.27	0.76	2.44	0.016
	12 th	73	3.61	0.79		
Taking the professional decision	11 th	58	3.37	0.58	3.87	0.000
	12 th	73	3.76	0.55		

Table (9) indicates statistically significant differences at the value ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the means of the career choice decision-making skill dimensions among high school students based on the academic level vary according to total t calculated value of (3.87) with a significance of (0.000). Concerning the availability of information dimension, the t value was (3.85). A significance level of (0.000), for the traditional dimension, the t value reached (3.21) and a significance level of (0.002), for the independency dimension, the t value was (2.43), and a significance level of (0.016), and finally, the t value for the involvement dimension was (2.44). The significance level was (0.016). These differences are in favor of the twelfth-grade students.

The researcher believes that this result reflects the fact that grade twelve students have to decide at the end of the academic year the future profession because it is the last year in their studies compared to the eleventh-grade students, who have a full year left for an opportunity to deliberate, consult others and see the details related to the future profession.

Result Discussion

The study is to recognize the ability level to take a vocational decision and its effect on the future occupation for a group of secondary schools students. The first questionnaire showed that the skill level to take a vocational level decision for the secondary school students was average, except the traditional aspect if it is high. The results of the second question that there are no statistical differences between the average of deciding according to the genders for the total score in all aspects for the side of the male except the traditional aspect where there was no statistical result. The third question, it indicates no statistical differences. Between the average of taking vocational decision according to the school stage which was from grade 12 students side when comparing the current study result with the studies, we found that the current one is distinguished to study the level of the skill of taking a vocational decision through measuring a group of aspects which showed the level of the members of the group clearly and in details. Also, we recognized the process of making a decision and its relation with the future occupation for the group. When comparing it with (al Ghazali 2019) (Swalih 2019) (Abu Assad 2017) and (al Zahra 2016), we found that it added a scientific value by dividing the level of the decision taken into the different aspects. Leading to recognize the types of the study on all aspects it was put for; the above studies didn't have a look on taking the vocational decision through the aspect except the study of (Abu Asaad 2017) we noticed that the result of (Al Zahra 2016) from the side of taking the vocational decision which was average. The agreement was because of the similarity of culture, environment, and the timing period. The study result came with the result of (al Ghazali 2019) in the differences for the male side because of the similarity of the social factors which has the highest role to make the males get more experience because of their interest in the future occupation. It was similar to the study of (Shumba and Noong 2012), which shows the teacher's role in increasing the student's awareness. This agreement came as a result of providing the students with information about the different occupations because students usually ask about. It agreed with the study of (Luzo et al.,1999) where there is a lack in the vocational information, which can be because of the lack of person who provides enough information for the students, also agreed with the study of (NOTA, SORESI 2004) and (Farvini 2004) where there are instructional programs which help in increasing the information and decreasing the student's vocational hesitation. It agreed with the study of (Mohammed and others 2010) from the information shortage and because there was no model to affect the vocational decision. Also, it differs from the study of (Al Saedi 2012) because the result was leading to the destination of grades 12 and 11 in the current study leads to differences for grade 12 because of the experience factor and the culture difference its variety. This study differs from the others in that it increases the awareness of researchers

Conclusions of the study

1- The participation of 12th and 11th grades students in making the career choice decision came at a medium level.

2- The availability of information is considered one of the most important aspects of professional decision-making. This feature has become present, and it is no longer absent as before, except that it needs to be further strengthened.

3. The involvement and participation of students in the professional decision are still far from being applied, as it has achieved the last rank between the dimensions and areas of professional decision-making.

4. The results indicated that the Arab patriarchal society still imposes its shadows on students in eleventh and twelfth grades.

5. The results also showed that the traditional methods of professional decision-making subject male and female subjects

Recommendations of the study:

In light of the results revealed here, the following recommendations were suggested:

1- Enhancing students' knowledge of information about future occupations and careers.

2-Working on increasing student's participation in the professional decision-making process.

3- Paying attention to the eleventh-grade students and starting directing them to future careers until they are ready at the end of the twelfth grade.

References

- Abu Hammad, N. (2008). *Psychological Counseling and Career Instruction*. New Books Science and Jadaa for University Book. Irbid. Jordan.
- AlBlooshi, R. (2007). Building a vocational training program based on Gillette's model and measuring its effectiveness in improving professional decision-making for tenth-grade students in the Sultanate of Oman. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Amman Arab University, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Issawi, A. (1986). *Educational and Vocational Guidance*. United Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Arab Bureau of Education for the Gulf States.
- Alkhatatneh, S. (2011). *Administrative Psychology*. (1st ed.). Jordan: Dar Al-Hamed for publication and distribution.
- Al-Khazali, M. (2019). Psychological pressure and its relationship with professional decision-making for middle school students. *Ahl Al-Bait*, (25), 552-581.
- AlSaadi, I. (2012). Vocational maturity and its relationship with the career decision making amongst high school students [Unpublished master's thesis]. Taibah University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- Alsawwat, W.(2010). Self-Efficacy and its Relationship with The Career Choice Decision Making Skill Among 1st Secondary Grade in Taif Governorate/ KSA: A Descriptive Predictive Study. *Educational and Psychological Studies. Journal of Faculty of Education / Zaqaziq*. 66 (1).
- Al-Zahra, A. (2016). Capability level on making career-related decisions among final year distinctive university students. [unpublished master's thesis]. The University of Eloued.
- Alzain, M. Abu As'ad, A. (2017). Career Decision Making Based on the Gellatt Model Among Secondary Stage Students in Jiza Province. *Educational Sciences Studies*. Vol 44, Issue 2.
- Barbar, A. (1996). *Administration: A Process and a System*. Ed 1. Beirut. University Institution for Studies and Publication.
- Eysenck, M.& Keane, M. (2000). *Cognitive Psychology: A Student's Handbook*. (6th ed.). England: Psychology Press.
- favini·Irma·B. N. (2004). A future that Fits Mi, Which School, Which Work·An Italian Experience of Vocational Guidance.
- Gati, I. &Krausz, M. (1996). A Taxonomy of Difficulties in Career Decision Making. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 43(4).
- Habib,A. (1997). *The Psychology of Decision Making*. (1st ed.). Cairo: Library of Alexandria.
- Jawdat,A. &Al-Ezza,S. (2012). *Career Choice Guidance and Theories*. (2nd ed.). Jordan: Dar Al Thaqafa For Publishing & Distributing.

- Luzzo et al. (2011). Evaluating Differences in College Students' Career Decision Making based on Disability Status. *Career Development Quarterly*, 48(2).
- Mohd, F. Salleh, A. & Mustapha, R. (2010). The Influence of Contextual Aspects on Career Decision Making of Malaysian Technical Students. Elsevier Ltd, 7(1).
- Nawafleh, A. (2014). The Effectiveness Program of Group Counseling Based on Holland's Theory of Career Aspirations and Strengthening the Development of Vocational Skills, Decision-Making at the Tenth Grade Students in Jordan. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis. The World Islamic Science & Educational University"
- Nota, L. & Soresi, S. (2004). Improving the Problem-Solving and Decision-Making Skills of a High Indecision Group of Young Adolescents: A Test of the "Difficult: No Problem!" Training. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 4(1).
- Sawaleh, N. (2019). Level of decision-making capabilities and its patterns. [unpublished master's thesis]. Mohamed Khider University.
- Shumba, A. & Naong, M. (2012). Factors Influencing Students' Career Choice and Aspirations in South Africa. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 33(2).
- UAE Educational System (2015-2017). School Education Stages and Paths. Available on: <https://u.ae/ar-ae/information-and-services/education/school-education>.

Author Information

Dr. Anas Mohammad Nawafleh

Alain University, United Arab Emirates

Dr. Hussein M. A. AL- Tarawneh

Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Dr. Haya Hussien M. TarawnehResearcher, Amman – Jordan
